

STUDY OF RAINFALL PATTERN & COMPUTATIONS OF DEPTH OF RAINFALL AND WEIGHTED MEAN RAINFALL FOR KARJAN DAM CATCHMENT AREA.

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ABSTRACT

The Gujarat state lies in the North-East corner of the coast of Western India. The rainfall pattern in the state varies drastically from north to south and east to west. The river Narmada is the largest river in Gujarat state and is considered the lifeline of the state. Karjan River is a major tributary of River Narmada. As there are number of structures being constructed across the river Narmada, a critical study is essential for studying the rainfall pattern for all the catchments of the tributaries of the river.

In this paper, it is proposed to study the rainfall pattern and derive the average depth for the catchment of Karjan River. For this study it is proposed to develop Thiessen polygons for Karjan Dam catchment area and from that average depth of rainfall is calculated for different rain gauge stations located within the catchment area.

KEY WORDS

Rainfall, Catchment, Average Depth of Rainfall, Thiessen polygon method.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- (1) Analysis of rainfall pattern for various rain-gauge stations.
- (2) To find out average depth of rainfall of Karjan Dam catchment area.

ABOUT THE STUDY AREA

Narmada, the largest West flowing river of the Peninsula, rises near Amarkantak in the Shahdol district of Pradesh at an elevation of 900 m in the Maikla range, Karjan River is a major tributary of Narmada. The catchment area of the river till its confluence with Narmada

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is 1489.25 sq km. The river Narmada is considered as the lifeline of Gujarat. Besides the Sardar Sarovar Project (SSP), it is also proposed to construct a weir at Garudeshwar and a barrage at Bhadbhut on the downstream of the Sardar Sarovar Dam.

There are several tributaries of the river Narmada. The river Karjan is one of the tributaries of the river Narmada. Catchment area of Karjan dam is 1403 sq km out of which an area of 355 sq km is intercepted by Bhatpur project and 31 sq km lies in Maharashtra. Hence the planned Catchment area for Karjan dam reduces to 1017 sq km.

The catchment area of Karjan Dam along with catchment areas of Sardar sarovar Dam and Proposed Bhadbhut barrage are given below in fig 1. For the analysis; data of rainfall are collected from State water data centre, Gandhinagar, and Narmada water resources and Kalpsar department, Gandhinagar.

Figure 1: Catchment area of Karjan Dam

RAINFALL PATTERN ANALYSIS

To find out average depth of rainfall for Karjan Dam catchment area, Thiessen polygon method is adopted for analysis. For that Thiessen polygons are developed from the available rainfall data for each rain gauge station (as given below).

Fig 2 to 12 shows the rainfall at each year for different rain gauge stations and right hand side fig. shows the constructed Thiessen polygon for Karjan dam catchment area.

Figure 2: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2000

Figure 3: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2001

Figure 4: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2002

Figure 5: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2003

Figure 6: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2004

Figure 6: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2005

Figure 7: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2006

Figure 8: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2007

Figure 9: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2008

Figure 10: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2009

Figure 11: Rainfall graph and Thiessen polygon for year 2010

The average depth of rainfall for each year using the Thiessen Polygon method as well as the Arithmetic Mean Method is obtained as shown in Table 1

Table 1 Average Depth of Rainfall in mm over Karjan Catchment

Year	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	Avg
By Thiessen Polygon Method	470	961	739	1529	1242	1265	2002	1670	1349	1191	1119	1231
By Arithmetic Mean Method	424	994	694	1507	1228	1280	1754	1600	1313	1004	1081	1171

DISCUSSIONS & CONCLUSIONS

The average depth of rainfall calculated using both the methods for a span of 11 years for all the years from 2000 to 2010. For most of the years, the values obtained by both the methods is very near to the value obtained by the other method, except for the years 2006 and 2009. The average depths obtained by the Thiessen Polygon method is slightly higher than that of the Arithmetic Mean method for all the years. Taking an average value for all the 11 years, we get Average depth of rainfall for Karjan Catchment as 1231 mm using Thiessen Polygon Method and 1171 mm using Arithmetic Mean Method.

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